

ASPECTS REGARDING THE MANAGEMENT OF THE DESIGN AND TESTING OF A NATURAL GAS MEASURING DEVICE

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Abstract

Purpose – Limiting or stopping unauthorized natural gas consumption on natural gas meters.

Methodology/approach - It is presented the impact that an unauthorized intervention has on the measuring device, its verification in the laboratory and the elaboration of some management procedures that will help to improve it.

Findings – Natural gas meters are quite vulnerable, and due to these unauthorized interventions safety in operation is endangered, and the damage caused is very high.

Research limitations/implications – Even if a lot of precautions are taken to stop this phenomenon, gas meters are of many types of construction and the possibilities for intervention are quite many.

Practical implications – Verification of measuring devices with unauthorized intervention in the metrology laboratory and determination of measurement errors.

Originality/value – Designing a new type of natural gas measuring device by developing management procedures with which to be able to reduce all known methods of fraud and to provide safety in operation.

Key words: gas meter, quality and risk management, prototype.

1. Introduction

In the distribution of natural gas, meters are a main element, because with their help we measure the amount of gas sold or bought. For this reason, it is very important that the gas meters be designed and constructed in such a way that their indication errors fall within the maximum allowed limits. This paper presents two methods of unauthorized intervention on a measuring device. Emphasis is placed on operational safety, prevention and the impact on the distribution company, as well as a set of management procedures that help reduce these interventions. For each intervention method, a meter measurement error is established in the metrology laboratory, this again meaning a loss for the distributor.

A case study was made regarding the analysis that emerged after the verification of the meters in the laboratory and an optimized meter is sketched that is able to prevent these interventions. Basically, in this paper we try to optimize a gas meter based on management procedures so that it can no longer be fraudulent, no longer represent a risk in operation and implicitly no longer cause damage to the distributor.

2. Literature review

The construction of the meter must be made of resistant materials that suffer little or no changes due to aging and that must be resistant to moisture and the corrosive action of gases. Meter housings must be constructed in such a way that they are watertight at the maximum operating pressure of the meter. (0.5 bar in our case). The meter must operate in normal outdoor conditions, subject to rain and solar radiation. The meters must be protected against interventions that could affect the measurement. They

must be constructed in such a way that any mechanical intervention from the outside produces a permanent deterioration of the metrological mark or of the meter, as the case may be. Gas meters whose numerical integrator only works for a certain direction of gas flow must have an arrow on its housing to indicate the direction of gas flow. With the help of some rules or procedures, a device can be imposed to prevent the gas from flowing in the opposite direction.

The meter must operate at the maximum flow in the time interval that is specified in the meter norm, without the changes of the metrological characteristics exceeding the limits prescribed in it. (NML 3-04-96)

The quality management of the gas meter can be defined as a set of coordinated activities aimed at controlling its quality. Quality management is done through quality planning, quality control, quality assurance and last but not least quality improvement. (Morariu, 2016)

From the perspective of the customer but also of the distribution company, it is important that the gas measurement is as accurate as possible. Even though gas meters are constantly being improved, they are quite vulnerable to outside action. A main factor is given by the economic component, a cheap meter cannot have all the elements of protection against a deliberate external action.

According to Law 123 of 2012, unauthorized intervention in the distribution system is a crime and is punished accordingly. The management of these interventions is quite elaborate and expensive.

Looking at this meter from the perspective of quality management, it must satisfy through all its technical and economic characteristics the purpose for which it was designed, that of measuring as accurately as possible. (Ilea and Stoica, 2020)

The role of this study and of the improvement to the gas meter is to help natural gas distributors to be aware of the risk they are subject to, so that they can manage these risks. Here we can see the connection between quality management and risk management, two branches of management that cannot exist without each other. (Risk management course)

In this paper, the product innovation is represented by the natural gas meter, and the identification of the problem for which the innovation is desired is represented by the unauthorized intervention. There are solutions to stop them and put them into practice. (Popescu, 2016)

The process management proposes planning the optimization activities of the new meter by improving the actual process; by innovating it, starting with the problems / criticisms brought to it, needs and expectations. The whole process is evaluated, the improvement opportunities are selected, the meter is optimized, and then the obtained performances are continuously monitored and evaluated. (Olaru, 2000)

Pantelemon Frasineanu proposes the introduction of smart meters on the market. An economic analysis was made of the benefits brought by this implementation, both quantitative and qualitative. Not only the implementation costs are quite high but also the costs for their maintenance. According to those presented, I believe that in addition to the smart side of the meters, the design must be as well done so that the fraud aspect must be at minimum. In the case of smart meters, if they are fraudulent with known methods, the economic impact can be up to 10 times higher, because of the price point from the classic ones. (Pantelemon, 2014)

The great professor of Romanian origin Joseph M. Juran reminds us that quality is everyone's problem. "If we do something, let's do it right from the start." These principles show us again the importance of designing and executing a meter that is qualitative at the highest level. This principle brings very good results, both for gas consumers and for the distributor. (Managementul Calitatii)

Risk management is a cyclical and continuous process. The risk is defined by the possibility of certain damages being created. The risk probability in this case is relatively high, and the impact of the risk is given by the financial damage caused but as well of that of the image (Managementul Riscului)

A gas meter must not have features that would facilitate fraudulent use, or the possibility of unintentional misuse. Measurement errors must not be overly influenced when flows or currents have values outside the controlled range. (NML 001-05)

According to ISO 9001: 2005, organizations must demonstrate that they have identified risks and take action to eliminate or limit their effects. To assess the risks, we must answer the following questions: what are the consequences? what is the probability of occurrence in the future? What are the factors that reduce the likelihood of risk occurrence? (ISO 9001:2015)

3. Unauthorized interventions and control management

3.1. Drilling the outlet connection of the measuring chamber

In this case, three holes were made in the outlet connection of the measuring chamber, with the aim of reducing the consumption of natural gas. An amount of gas that is not measured passes through the 3 holes. To perform this type of intervention, the meter must be removed from the installation. The damage done can be quite large.

Figure 1. Drilling the outlet connection of the measuring chamber

3.2. Intervention on the metrological mark and the numerical integrator

In this case, intervention was made on the metrological mark that secures the cover of the recording mechanism and on the cover of the recording mechanism. Basically, the cover of the recording mechanism was detached and part of the gear teeth of the digital integrator were cut. Through this method, the natural gas meter still records only a part of the real natural gas consumption.

Figure 2. Intervention on the integrator and cutting the gear teeth of the mechanical index

From the two examples of unauthorized interventions highlighted above, it can be easily seen that safety in operation is endangered. The damage is great and can be defined as a sum of the amount of unmeasured and invoiced gas, destroyed measuring devices, costs of identifying unauthorized

interventions, travel and maintenance costs, changing the meters and last but not least salary costs of the staff.

The competitive management of this product proposed a set of procedures with the help of which we can stop this phenomenon.

3.3. Checking the meters in the metrology laboratory

After finding the unauthorized intervention, the gas meters are taken to a legal metrology laboratory and are checked with the help of a bell installation or other types of installations.

The meters are taken to the laboratory, kept for acclimatization and placed on a checkpoint. Their operation is compared with a standard, in our case the standard is represented by the bell installation. The comparison of the air volumes measured by the bell installation with the air volumes measured by the gas meters is made only if the two measured air / gas volumes are related to the same thermodynamic contents, absolute temperature and absolute pressure. The meters must operate and measure the amount of gas circulated within the maximum allowed limits.

With the help of this installation the operating errors for the 2 methods of unauthorized interventions mentioned above can be determined. Operating errors show us the amount of gas not measured and not billed.

The management of a metrology laboratory must ensure the competence of metrologists who perform metrological verifications. (NML 004-05)

Figure 3. Installation of checking gas meters with bell

4. Case study

4.1. Testing natural gas meters in the metrology laboratory

For the 2 cases of unauthorized intervention described above, the gas meters were checked in the metrology laboratory to see their operation and to establish the errors given in operation. (NML 3-05-96)

The measurement errors of the gas meters are determined for 3 flows: the minimum flow **Q_{min}** = which represents the minimum flow that the meter can record; transition flow **Q_t** = $0.2 \cdot Q_{\max}$ = represents the flow between the minimum and maximum flow; maximum flow rate **Q_{max}** = represents the maximum flow rate that the gas meter can measure. (NML 004-05)

The measurement of the gas volume with the deformable wall meters is carried out with the help of the measuring chambers with deformable walls, with or without built-in temperature conversion devices. (Stoica, and Feier, 2016)

Measurement errors are calculated with the following formulas and are divided into 2 categories, gas meters without temperature conversion devices and gas meters equipped with mechanical temperature conversion devices.

For gas meters that do not have a mechanical conversion device:

$$e_i = \left(\frac{V_i}{V_E} \times \frac{P_i}{P_E} - 1 \right) \times 100 (\%); \text{ (NML 004-05)}$$

V_i is the volume of air measured by the meter i , V_E is the volume of air measured by the standard, P_i is the absolute air pressure at the inlet to meter i and P_E is the absolute air pressure in the standard;

For gas meters that have in their component a mechanical conversion device:

$$e_i = \left(\frac{V_i}{V_E} \times \frac{P_i}{P_E} \times \frac{T_E}{T_i} - 1 \right) \times 100 (\%); \text{ (NML 004-05)}$$

T_E is the absolute temperature under the bell, T_i is the air temperature through the meter i .

Table 1. Tolerated errors according to NML 004-05 (NML 004-05)

Test flow (m ³ /h)	Tolerated error (%)
Q_{max}	-1,5...+1,5
Q_t	-1,5...+1,5
Q_{min}	-3,5...+3,5

Table 2. The results of the analysis of the first meter in the laboratory (3.1)

Counter	Case 1 (3.1.)				
P atm (mbar)	993				
	Q_{max}	Q_t		Q_{min}	
T amb °C	20,6	T amb °C	20,6	T amb °C	20,6
T air standard °C	20,6	T air standard °C	20,6	T air standard °C	20,6
T output °C	20,5	T output °C	20,5	T output °C	21,4
Δp (mbar)	1,96				
Volume standard (dm ³)	400	Volume standard (dm ³)	100	Volume standard (dm ³)	20
Index initial (dm ³)	3238172,3				
Final index Q_{max} (dm ³)	3238429,4	Index final $0,2Q_{max}$	3238430,4	Final index Q_{min}	3238430,4
Error (%)	-34,48	Error (%)	-98,98	Error (%)	-100

Table 3. The results of the analysis of the second meter in the laboratory (3.2)

Counter	Case 2 (3.2.)				
P atm (mbar)	983				
	Q_{max}	Q_t		Q_{min}	
T amb °C	18,5	T amb °C	18,5	T amb °C	18,5
T air standard °C	18,5	T air standard °C	18,5	T air standard °C	18,5
T output °C	18,4	T output °C	18,4	T output °C	18,4
Δp (mbar)	1,96				
Volume standard (dm ³)	400	Volume standard (dm ³)	100	Volume standard (dm ³)	20
Index initial (dm ³)	4288428,5				
Final index Q_{max} (dm ³)	4288559,0	Final index $0,2Q_{max}$	4288591,5	Final index Q_{min}	4288598,2
Error (%)	-66,98	Error (%)	-67,11	Error (%)	-69,09

Analyzing the data in table 2. we noticed that for the first method of unauthorized intervention (3.1) the results are catastrophic. When the meter operates at a maximum flow rate, it records 34.48% less than the amount of gas consumed, when it operates at the transition flow rate it registers 98.98% less, and at the minimum flow rate it no longer records the amount of gas circulated, the error being -100%.

Analyzing the data from table 3. we notice that for the second method of unauthorized intervention (3.2) the results are also catastrophic. When the meter operates at a maximum flow rate, it registers with 66.98% less than the amount of gas consumed, when it operates at the transition flow rate it registers with 67.11% less, and at the minimum flow rate it registers with 69.09 % less.

Neither of the two meters falls within the normal operating limits shown in Table 1.

By the calculations presented above, the total losses of the approximation meter can be calculated. In addition to the losses mentioned above, the costs for laboratory verification are added. Laboratories must have a set of management procedures to verify the meters that must be observed accurately.

From this analysis it is necessary to draw up an impact study to indicate the total losses generated by this phenomenon of fraud, a study that includes the damages resulting from the differences between actual and measured consumption, but also the costs related to on-site inspection, team travel , disassembly - assembly, laboratory verification, etc.

4.2. Design of a prototype natural gas meter

With these results, a new natural gas meter was designed and built as a prototype, which would be able to stop unauthorized intervention.

A set of management procedures has been developed to help optimize the meter so that it is as high quality and has as few vulnerabilities as possible.

A meter has been designed to have a sensor capable of triggering a silent alarm in case of unauthorized disassembly of the meter embedded in the input and output connections. This alarm is to be transmitted to the distributor in real time or when the meter is read, depending on the chosen constructive variant. This procedure prevents damage of any kind inside the meter and implicitly would have prevented the unauthorized intervention from point 3.1.

Mounting some sieves on the input and output connections. If these sieves are damaged we can conclude that someone intervened or tried to intervene on the meter.

Another management procedure proposes the integration of the recording mechanism in the metal body of the meter. In this way the gearing and indicating rollers of the recording mechanism are secured, and the intervention method from point 3.2 could have been prevented.

The meter is able to transmit the index automatically via a GSM card or via low frequency radio waves.

Installation of anti-fraud stickers to seal the electronic parts or on the cover of the recording mechanism on classic meters.

Creating an orifice in the lid of the recording mechanism for classic meters through which the distributor can seal its integrator with a disposable seal.

The incorporation of a throttle that prevents the flow of gas in the opposite direction, is able to disconnect gas consumption and trigger a silent alarm. This solution is practical for reverse meter mounting attempts. (Ilea, 2019)

Using temperature and pressure sensors for the most accurate measurement.

The meter can be optionally equipped with the elements mentioned above as required.

Figure 4. Gas meter prototype

5. Conclusions

Following the presented ones, the gas distribution companies must understand the importance of the quality of a natural gas meter, both from a constructive and a functional point of view. Meter quality is a must.

Natural gas consumers must understand the dangers to which they are exposed by producing this phenomenon, safety in operation being the most important in the end.

We can see that natural gas meters are quite vulnerable to external interventions, causing significant losses. In order to prevent or diminish this phenomenon, it is necessary to invest in more efficient measuring devices.

There is a need to implement a complex quality and risk management system. The two branches must complement each other. As advantages of using the new type of meter we can list: reduction of money losses generated by unauthorized interventions, reduction of unauthorized interventions, reallocation of staff dealing with these checks in other key points of the company, elimination or reduction of expenses for detecting, solving and checking meters with unauthorized intervention

At the same time, it is necessary to carry out a study regarding the manufacturing costs, to be within reasonable limits, able to ensure the profit of the builders but also of the handlers (maintenance and assembly companies). One possibility for which some research has already been undertaken is based on the DFMA, which helps to choose the materials from which the meter is made and to choose the most suitable assembly procedure.

References

NML 3-04-96

Legal Metrological Norm - Gas meters. General technical and metrological conditions.

Morariu, C.O.

2016

Sistemul de Management al Calitatii. Tipografia Universitatii Transilvania din Braşov, pp 39-41.

Ilea, P.E. and Stoica, A.

2020

Some aspects of quality and risk management in natural gas measurement, IOP Conf. Ser.: Mater. Sci. Eng. 749 012016.

Risk management course

http://silvic.usv.ro/cursuri/managementul_riscului.pdf, accessed in June 2020.

Popescu, M.

2016

Managementul Inovarii. Editura Universitatii Transilvania din Braşov

Olaru, M.

2000

Tehnici și instrumente utilizate în managementul calității, Editura Economică, București

Pantelemon, F.

2014

Monitoringul consumului de gaze pe piața Republicii Moldova prin contorizarea inteligentă, Analele Institutului National de cercetari Economice, nr. 2, pp. 45-50

Managementul Calitatii

Managementul Calitatii - Suport de curs. Editura Universitatii de Vest Vasile Goldis Arad, pp 11-13.

Managementul Riscului

Managementul Riscului - Suport de curs. Editura Facultatii de Silvicultura Suceava, pp 3-6.

NML 001-05

Norma Metrologica Legala - Cerinte metrologice si tehnice comune mijloacelor de masurare supuse controlului metrologic legal.

ISO 9001:2015

Managementul Calitatii.

NML 004-05

Norma Metrologica Legala - Contoare de gaz si dispozitive de conversie a volumului.

NML 3-05-96

Norma Metrologica Legala - Contoare de gaz cu pereti deformabili.

Stoica, A., Feier, D.

2016

Aparate de măsură și control în industria gazelor naturale. Editura „Universității Lucian Blaga” din Sibiu, Sibiu, România.

Ilea, P.E.

2019

Some aspects of gas meter quality and analyzing the sustainability of a gas meter element , IOP Conf. Ser.: Mater. Sci. Eng. 568 012063